

Coordinated Research Infrastructures Building Enduring Life-science services - CORBEL

Deliverable D3.8.

Report on implementation, including economic model and solutions for sustainability

WP3 – Community-driven cross-infrastructure joint research - Medical

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Executive Summary

This paper assesses options on how to build upon the work performed by ECRIN in developing a demonstrator repository in DSpace and assessing its performance as an example of best practice. In particular, it considers how any approach may be made sustainable.

The five options considered are:

1. To create a community of practice by making the demonstrator, academic work around repositories and quality criteria, and perhaps advice, publicly available to assist others in development of repositories and influence culture, practices, perhaps certification and even regulations around data storage and data sharing;
2. To utilise the repository for storing and analysing clinical trial data, either that of ECRIN or of others;
3. To further develop the demonstrator into a state-of-the-art operational repository for mass data sharing, perhaps in conjunction with EOSC-Life;
4. Building upon the work on the creation of and assessment of the demonstrator, ECRIN could develop, offer and run a costed repository support service, specialising in sensitive data based upon Figshare;
5. Development of repository services in the context of a model for future rapid response framework for health emergency readiness.

For each of these options the elements of viability, utility and long-term sustainability are considered.

The first option appears to be of great potential benefit relative to the costs involved in set-up and operations. The extent to which further work is done in this area would depend upon ongoing assessment of needs, uptake and resources available, but no upfront commitment in terms of time or resources would be required and further developments could be implemented as appropriate in the future. These facets of low-risk and scale-ability make it an attractive option. Moreover, pursuing it does not preclude any of the others and may in fact be complementary to any of these. For this reason, it is recommended.

The second option does not appear to be easily practicable due to considerable complexities with regard to clinical trial data sharing, especially in Europe's multi-national and complex legislative setting.

The third option would require considerable funding, both for the development of the operational repository, which may be attainable by means of an EOSC-Life Open Call or other funding instruments, and more significantly for the continuing operations of the repository. This would not be easy to secure and without it there would little to no long-term utility to the project. A convincing strategy to secure this must be developed in order to proceed.

A further significant issue to be addressed in this scenario is the utility of duplicating resources or services already provided by other parties, for example Vivli, in respect of the scale of the potential project, and RDR (UCL Research Data Repository) as a repository planning to interact with the European Open Science Cloud.

Further consideration should be given to how the operational repository would meet important needs that are not and likely will not be met by other parties. Potentially significant issues in assessing this

are the difference between pseudonymised and anonymised data, legal problems with EU data being held on servers based in the US, and the particular capacities provided (e.g. with the European Open Science Cloud) that offer unique advantages.

This option would only be viable if significant long-term funders expressed serious interest. It would be useful to investigate this and, if opportunities were identified, to adapt a plan to the funders' more specific requirements. Currently there is no convincing strategy to secure this and so it is not a viable route at the moment.

The fourth option would build upon the work performed in the first option. It would require modest capital outlay in developing the Figshare application, but the operational costs would be variable according to demand and thus quickly scalable. Analysis indicates that the services would be useful, in reasonable demand, and economically viable. Further developments such as certifications or more comprehensive methods of advice and best practice guides could be implemented based upon the initial service provision. This option, if funding for development is available, could be pursued and offers utility. However, many of the useful elements of this option would also be served by the fifth option, which is even more attractive. Were the fifth option to be developed, some of the repository support services would form a complementary part of the operation.

The fifth option, offering the most effective and important long-term deliverable, involves the immediate development of the repository in the context of a model for future rapid response framework for health emergency readiness. This model would include services, protocols and legal frameworks established to facilitate rapid re-use of the system. Given the positive environment with funders and potential collaborators it is recommended that this be pursued.

Project objectives

This deliverable contributes to the following objective of Task 3:

Developing procedures to provide the scientific community with access, upon request, to the patient-level data from previous clinical trials for re-analyses, secondary analyses and meta-analyses and to test them in a pilot/demonstrator.

Detailed report on the Deliverable

Background

Definition of the Task and the Deliverable

In Task 3.3.3. ECRIN developed a pilot/demonstrator repository for clinical trial data. The pilot led the foundations of a re-analysis/meta-analysis enabling repository developed to work with patient data in a research setting.

Task 3.3.4. involves an assessment of the cost and added value of this pilot/demonstrator and proposals for a sustainable model.

The cost and sustainability of developing a system enabling re-analyses of clinical trials, secondary analyses, and meta-analyses at the patient level data has to be assessed. In particular, there may be cases where running meta-analyses based on patient level data instead of aggregated data would not bring significant added value with regards to the cost of the procedure.

The economic model of access to patient level data should therefore be discussed within the multi-stakeholder taskforce, in the presence of organisations funding clinical trials or meta-analyses, and secondary users of clinical trial data. A central part of the discussion will be the cost of data extraction and analysis, leading to proposals for a sustainable economic solution for this activity.

This Deliverable, D3.8, consists of a report on implementation, including an economic model and solutions for the long-term sustainability of a repository for patient-level data from clinical trials.

For discussion of data repositories, it will be useful to standardise terminology as detailed by C. Ohmann in BMJ Open, 2017¹: data generators and data requestors will be the terms used throughout this task and in materials referring to and forming part of the repository (dummy or otherwise) and related resources.

Demonstrator

Within CORBEL Task 3.3.3 ECRIN has developed a demonstrator repository for clinical trial data based upon DSpace. The main objective was to assess the demonstrator repository against defined quality criteria and requirements. This demonstrator was filled in with anonymised open available data from the internet.

The results have been summarised in a detailed report “Assessment of a demonstrator repository for individual clinical trial data built upon DSpace”². The conclusions were: “Technically the system was able to support most of the pre-defined requirements for good IPD access, though there are areas where support could be improved. Of course, in a real repository, appropriate policies and procedures would be needed to direct the use of the available technical features. A technical evaluation should therefore be seen as indicating a system’s potential, rather than being a definite assessment of its suitability. DSpace clearly has considerable potential in this context and appears a suitable base for further exploration of the issues around storing sensitive data.”

The next step to be dealt with in WT3.3.4 is to develop an assessment and business plan for the further development and maintenance of this demonstrator repository. This will detail next steps for turning the existing repository into a repository for individual participant data from clinical trials, for routine use with real data.

The following statement from the report details why the outcome of the assessment indicates possibilities of further utility to be gained from work relating to the demonstrator:

As detailed in the report “Assessment of a DSpace demonstrator repository for individual clinical trial data.”², the operational feasibility of the repository is high.

“In general the performance of the DSpace Repository in supporting sensitive personal data such as that from clinical trials was strong, with 14 requirements demonstrated (74%). This included strong support for different file types and metadata systems, a range of access control systems, including embargoes and granular access management, an integrated persistent identifier scheme plus support for other identifiers like DOIs, and good support for data management in the long-term.

Of the two areas that were not demonstrated at all, the first – the inability to incorporate de-identification tools in the submission workflow – is arguably an over ambitious requirement. Although general techniques certainly exist for de-identification this should normally be an exercise that is

planned, documented and tested on a study-by-study basis, rather than an automatic process. Having links available to de-identification resources is probably a more realistic requirement.

The second missing requirement, the lack of a self-attestation system, is a feature that some data generators might want to use, as it requires much less administrative overhead than setting up access rights for groups and individuals. It would require an administrator to define the fields required for self-attestation and, like user registration, it could be backed up by a system requiring confirmation of the email address given. Given the range of other access options available in DSpace it may not be a serious omission, but it is a missing feature that would 'be nice to have'.

Illustrative Example Model, Operational Repository, Repository Support Service or Development within a Rapid Response Framework Related to COVID-19

There are five possible outcomes for the pilot/demonstrator developed in Task 3.3.3. The first option is a process of dissemination/implementation of good practice for repositories, for which the technical output developed would function as an example.

The second option and third options are to utilise the technical structure developed in the Task to provide an operational repository for real data.

The fourth option is to build upon the work on the creation of and assessment of the demonstrator, whereby ECRIN could use an existing repository system installed and applied for ECRIN purposes based upon FigShare and perhaps develop, offer and run a costed repository support service, specialising in sensitive data.

The fifth option involves the immediate development of the repository in the context of a model for future rapid response framework for health emergency readiness. This model would include services, protocols and legal frameworks established to facilitate rapid re-use of the system.

Following the development of the pilot, much of the value of the first output is already generated, including the methodology for assessment of repositories. Consideration must now be given to the dissemination and utilisation of the example and to ensuring sustainability in terms of the maintaining the important functions of the demonstrator and in being able to adapt to technical changes or developments where necessary.

The second and third options, involving the creation and maintenance of an operational repository, offer significant further benefits but also involves more complex issues. Specifically, there are three very significant factors that weigh on the feasibility of the approach, namely permissions, funding and utility. These are expanded upon below

Permission to use data

There could be problems adding ECRIN's data to the repository, as data belong to the sponsors and they would need to be convinced to transfer data to a repository. On the other hand, there is some interest in having ECRIN as provider for data sharing tools. While this could otherwise be a significant launch product, the problem of access to the data hampers it. While ECRIN was a pioneer in requiring investigators to agree to share their data, in practice this is currently very difficult for reasons of standard practice, national and EU regulations and time periods to obtain data from data generators.

For any other clinical data there are significant issues both with persuading investigators to share their data, incentivising data sharing, and the legal issues surrounding data sharing and consent.

Funding

The development would require substantial resources, analysis of which follows later in the document. It is likely to take place after the end of the CORBEL project and would require either other funding or In-Kind staff commitments (e.g. from ECRIN). The ability to secure sufficient funding for ongoing maintenance after the development and initiation of the project is key to its success.

The issue of approaching EOSC to provide (potentially with EOSC funding) an implemented repository that is operational as well as a model of best practice was discussed.

Utility

In order to avoid duplicating existing resources, it is important to assess what elements and services are provided that are not and will not be provided by others, e.g. Vivli. The particular differences and advantages should be analysed, and a formal or informal survey of potential user groups should be performed to measure the perceived need and likely uptake for this development.

The issues and benefits relating to the third option are considered in section 3.2.4.

The feasibility and potential benefits of the fourth and fifth options are detailed in the following sections.

Description of Work

Methodology for Assessment of Outputs

In order to assess the costs, issues, funding sources, environment and opportunities relating to repositories for clinical trial data, we conducted a thorough literature review and interviews and discussions with expert parties, including directors of three significant repositories (BioLINCC, Edinburgh DataShare and Vivli).

This information was used to assess:

1. The feasibility of generating each component;
2. The incremental utility of each component (as a sustainable element);
3. The incremental costs of each component (as a sustainable element); and
4. Risk factors relating to each element.

Once this was done SWOT analyses were produced. These provide relevant information to consider in order to decide upon the best route to pursue, including details of further information that may need to be obtained to get a better picture of the possibilities (e.g. surveys of potential users, expressed interest from funders).

The final decision regarding how best to proceed is to be taken by ECRIN, as the party providing the work, and by any funding bodies involved.

Dummy Repository as Illustrative Example (Option 1)

Functions and Operations

Users

The pilot would be of use to all those developing repositories, to achieve compliance with good practice but also for data generators to support their decision to transfer data to a repository of high quality.

In addition, it could also be referred to and inform the work of academics in the field.

Services provided

The data and documents provided by ECRIN on its DSpace demonstrator repository website are already provided, enabling interested parties to engage with and learn from the illustrative example.

Additional services may include interacting with repository developers/users, and researchers.

Existing qualification / certification systems of repositories

Given the lack of a consensus about the services required from a data repository, each organisation has implemented its own policies and systems to meet its own priorities. Greater harmonisation of practices within repositories, coupled with the implementation of quality criteria for repositories may diminish the reluctance of many researchers to share the data from their studies, thus promoting data-sharing, discoverability, and re-use.

Different approaches/systems have been applied to assess the quality of repositories dedicated to data sharing. Using the journal *Scientific Data* as a case study, Hrynaszkiewicz et al.³ proposed and showed examples of changes to the format and peer-review process for journal articles to more robustly link them to data that are only available on request. They also proposed additional features for data repositories to better accommodate non-public clinical datasets, including Data Use Agreements (DUAs).

Burton et al.⁴ have introduced the term “Data Safe Haven” and have given a meaningful interpretation: A Data Safe haven “is a repository in which useful but potentially sensitive data may be kept securely under governance and informatics systems that are fit-for-purpose and appropriately tailored to the nature of the data being maintained, and may be accessed and utilised by legitimate users undertaking work and research contributing to biomedicine, health and/or to ongoing development of healthcare systems”. 12 criteria have been developed to characterise what is meant by ‘Data Safe Haven’.

The Core Trustworthy Data Repositories Requirements are intended to reflect the characteristics of trustworthy repositories. As such, all requirements are mandatory and are equally weighted, standalone items. Although some overlap is unavoidable, duplication of evidence sought among requirements has been kept to a minimum where possible. The choices contained in checklists (e.g., repository type and curation level) are not considered to be comprehensive, and additional space is provided in all cases for the applicant to add ‘other’ (missing) options. This and any comments given may then be used to refine such lists in the future. The CoreTrustSeal Board offers all interested data repositories a core-level certification based on the DSA–WDS Core Trustworthy Data Repositories Requirements catalogue and procedures. CoreTrustSeal Data Repository certification replaces the DSA certification and the WDS certification of Regular Members.

The aim of an initiative of Science Europe was to develop a set of core requirements for data management plans (DMPs), as well as a list of criteria for the selection of trustworthy repositories where researchers can store their data for sharing. In light of the development of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and an increasing tendency towards data sharing, these requirements and criteria should help to harmonise rules on data management throughout Europe. This will aid researchers in complying with research data management requirements even when working with different research funders and research organisations. None of the approaches described above is sufficient to classify the quality of repositories for clinical trial data, as pointed out by Banzi et al⁵ and in the F1000 research paper². However, they provide basic requirements for repositories and some activities can be seen as complementary to our approach.

Needs met

The development of repositories for IPD is relatively new and there are many questions about repository characteristics and quality, data sharing, technical possibilities, and repository structure to be addressed. This demonstrator and associated information will help to advance the level of understanding and assessment at an academic level and also assist both technical developers and operators of repositories and users. The project addresses the needs of both contributors of data and users of data.

Other Benefits

There is scope for potential complementarity with development of new or best practice methods of analysis. If there is interaction with repository users and developers, then the questions asked and feedback given could be useful for ECRIN in learning more about the user and developer requirements, problems and insights related to repositories.

This work may help in the development of methodologies and applications for the assessment and possible certification of repositories. It may also have some impact in working to change culture and standards around data sharing and storage, conventions, standards of practice, etc.

Ownership

The key assets are the repository itself, the related analyses and documents, the time of relevant experts and some mode of giving advice/dealing with queries.

The data and documents provided by ECRIN on its DSpace demonstrator repository website will be released under an open data attribution licence to be specified.

The published papers will be publicly available, but the means of dissemination and communication (eg. a dedicated area of a website and some communications or technical work) may be held by different parties.

As the pilot was developed within the CORBEL project, it could be expected that the information service will be provided on the CORBEL website. This, however, is not likely to be sustainable beyond the project end.

In 2020 the CORBEL Executive Board developed a common website for the Life Science RIs in place of the CORBEL website once the project has ended, to cluster information from the RIs. The information could be made available here, but the long-term sustainability and the ability to adequately host and maintain the pilot repository is yet to be ascertained.

It is possible that a foundation or philanthropic funding may assume ownership of these tasks, but funding for maintenance rather than development is hard to procure and the costs associated with this maintenance are unlikely to be so substantial as to warrant significant investment of time and effort in seeking such support.

ECRIN could be effective owner of this operation, providing such in-kind hours as are determined reasonable and hosting the repository and the information. This could be on an area of ECRIN's own website, or on a separate website if this offers better communication and dissemination opportunities that justify the cost of building a designated website.

Feasibility and Operational Requirements

The papers produced on the repository and good practices will feasibly be publicly available and accessible both through publication in academic journals. They may also be made accessible either on the ECRIN and/or CORBEL websites or on the site hosting the demonstrator.

Access to the programming and the dummy repository requires hosting and maintenance but these functions fall within operations already performed by ECRIN, although additional costs for set up and hosting the demonstrator would be incurred, estimated to be in the range of 1,000 Euros and 3,000 Euros per annum respectively. DSpace materials, and/or the proposed CORBEL website, so would not require significant incremental work, resources or costs.

Additional services, information and/or advice (about technical details and data best practices) would require ongoing employment of technically skilled staff with specialised knowledge. This work would be complementary to work otherwise performed and would be discretionary in terms of the resources to be committed. Therefore, there is no cost or commitment problem preventing feasible operations.

The ongoing decisions to make constant developments or adaptations in response to technological developments, insights from other developments, insights from academic work and/or insights from users through interactions (possibly through some form of Wiki system) would depend upon perceived utility and available resources (almost entirely in terms of person time). While doing so may increase the value of the resources, no commitment need be made to guarantee this, additional work would be incrementally beneficial, not essential, to a sustained resource.

There would be significant costs in terms of technical and legal advice and in terms of time and resources if the decision was made either to:

- Implement a Wiki system allowing constructive development of principles, insights, knowledge and technical issues; or
- Provide guidance on issues arising from changes to the regulatory environment or standard practices (particularly relating to data protection).

Neither of these functions are required, and either could be implemented or considered in future as additional beneficial elements to be added to the resources. They represent additional opportunities that could be assessed following the sharing of the core resources.

Assessment of Utility as a Sustainable Entity

There are a significant and growing number of repositories being developed/upgraded that could in principle) benefit from examples of best practice. There are serious prevalent issues which this could help to address.

It is difficult to gauge the utility of the repository when operational, as this would depend upon the number of visitors, the perceived and actual value of the information imparted, the level of constructive interaction and an assessment of the influence on other designs and operating procedures.

However, as detailed below, the basic costs of hosting the information and the in-kind hours ECRIN could provide are modest and could readily be incorporated as complementary to other activities. Therefore, the provision of the example and related assessments and guidelines should easily be sustainable.

Should a more comprehensive service be envisaged, with more user interaction, updates, further examples, etc. this would involve greater costs and is unlikely to produce corresponding revenue. Such additional services would be discretionary and could be assessed based upon capacity in terms of in-kind labour and resources. A system for gauging and/or reviewing the utility of additional elements that is effective but not overly burdensome in terms of time or resources would need to be developed.

Requirements for Sustainability

The published documents and ECRIN's DSpace demonstrator repository website are available to all interested parties and do not require sustaining beyond ECRIN continuing to host the website. DSpace is Open Source software so no licence fees are required. Given ECRIN's close involvement with the project, their commitment to continuing to host the website is likely.

If elements to be sustained include being a best practice example and continuing to develop and share information about quality criteria for repositories, then there may be some further requirements to sustain this activity. Communication and dissemination, updating and revising the pilot repository, and interacting with users and developers would require both commitment of person time by ECRIN and the continuing availability of staff with appropriate expertise.

Assessment of Costs

The costs of hosting a website and of providing access to the demonstrator would require capital and human outlay. The information can be hosted on either the website already established by ECRIN, at additional costs estimated to be in the range of 1,000 Euros for set up and 3,000 Euros per annum for hosting, and storage costs, or on the site to be established by CORBEL post project end. No further development costs are required.

The costs in terms of time or resources would be those associated with communication and dissemination, with further work on enhancing the demonstrator, with responses to queries and interaction with users and manufacturers. All of these activities are entirely discretionary both in performance and in the level of time to commit. They are primarily activities that will require resources in terms of time for qualified staff. ECRIN would have the ability to be flexible in providing this as desired and would have to make no commitment.

The only significant commitment in terms of resources would be the upgrading or amending the repository either in response to technical updates, or to address flaws and areas for improvement. These costs would again be in terms of human resources, provided that ECRIN retains individuals with the proper expertise, or else in terms of payment to a subcontractor.

Given the assessment of the repository and the relative stability and security of DSpace it is unlikely that these costs in terms of time or resources would be material.

Assessment of Funding Sources

User fees for access to the information and the repository would be unusual and appear to be at odds with the purpose of the project.

The overall costs in terms of time or resources are both low and highly discretionary, mainly to be provided by ECRIN in terms of labour and website hosting. The costs involved even in pursuing and trying to arrange philanthropic funding, industry partnerships or other funding measures would probably exceed any benefit to be gained.

The ongoing costs of maintaining these outputs appear to be too small to warrant the complexities of pursuing and implementing project-specific funding. However, if 'bundled' with other assets or sources of information there may be a more plausible case.

Risk Factors and Mitigating Measures

Risk factors include:

- There is always some risk of technological obsolescence with such developments, but there is no reason to suspect that this significantly affects the demonstrator;
- Major changes to regulatory environment and/or common standards (especially regarding data protection);
- Lack of take-up by users;
- Users not using the same system (there would still be best practice illustrative benefits, but technical illustrative benefits would be reduced);
- Lack of awareness of the output or failure to generate awareness of the utility of the output; and
- Difficulties in access and/or communication preventing large-scale productive use/reference.

Where applicable, these risks could be mitigated by focusing on communication regarding the resources.

SWOT Analysis

<p style="text-align: center;">STRENGTHS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrator active and available • <u>DSpace</u> demonstrator website active and operation • Minimal costs for maintenance • Discretionary and scalable according to demand 	<p style="text-align: center;">WEAKNESSES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No revenue <u>model</u> • Limited utility compared to other options • Claiming “best practice” requires broad consensus, not yet achieved
<p style="text-align: center;">OPPORTUNITIES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interaction with other repository developers and users • Contribute to the discussion about quality assessment and certification of repositories for clinical trial data. • Complementarities with ECRIN’s activities and communications (and with those of the CORBEL RIs generally) • Utility as a tool in education and training activities 	<p style="text-align: center;">THREATS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different systems being used • Lack of take up by users

Operational Repository (Option 2 & 3)

Scale of Repository to be considered

Initially it needs to be established what basic types of operation would be possible and warrant further investigation.

In the initial planning two possibilities were considered:

1. to utilise the repository for storing and analysing clinical trial data, either that of ECRIN or of others; and
2. to further develop the demonstrator into a state-of-the-art operational repository for mass data sharing, perhaps in conjunction with EOSC-Life.

The first option does not appear to be easily practicable due to considerable complexities with regard to clinical trial data sharing. While ECRIN now requires that data generated in clinical trials with which they are associated be shared, in practice this can take considerable time to be effected (perhaps even after 5 and 10 year follow up studies) and it was judged that there is currently an insufficient amount of this data to make the option worthwhile.

The second option would require considerable funding, both for the development of the operational repository, which may be attainable by means of an EOSC-Life Open Call or other funding instruments, and more significantly for the continuing operations of the repository. This would not be easy to secure and without it there would be little to no long-term utility to the project. A convincing strategy to secure this must be developed in order to proceed.

Use of IPD

Cost and sustainability of developing a system enabling re-analyses of clinical trials, secondary analyses, and meta-analyses at the patient level data has to be assessed.

The costs of running a system that enables re-analyses of clinical trials, secondary analyses, and meta-analyses at the patient level need to be considered as set against the costs of doing so using aggregated data.

Value of storing data and using data at the individual patient level

Within the CORBEL project a multi-stakeholder task force involving a wide range of experts developed a consensus document on the sharing and reuse of individual participant data from clinical trials¹. The task force developed 10 principles for data sharing in clinical trials, the first of which being “P1: The provision of individual participant data should be promoted, incentivised and resourced so that it becomes the norm in clinical research. Plans for data sharing should be described prospectively, and be part of study development from the earliest stages.”

In 2017 The World Health Organization (WHO) published a joint statement which also stressed the importance of sharing IPD: “The benefit of sharing individual participants’ data (IPD) and the facilitation of research through greater access to primary datasets is a principle which we consider important.

We will support activities that enable the development of explicit ethical and legal frameworks that govern data collection and use and enable development of international norms and standards for sharing of IPD from clinical trials.”⁶

An analysis of the advantages of this approach is available in the Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions version 6.0 (updated July 2019)⁷.

Attitudes to and use of IPD by data generators and other stakeholders

There are increasing efforts to incentivise and/or mandate the sharing of IPD from clinical trials by stakeholders in trials and national and international bodies. Work performed under the CORBEL project has examined ways to further encourage this, by policy, education and incentives, and stressed the importance of continuing to create an environment where this becomes standard.

It was shown by Vickers⁸ in 2016 that there has been a very significant change in trialists’ attitudes towards data sharing – “a tectonic shift in attitudes” over the preceding decade.

The table below produced by Tenoir et al.⁹ also indicates the increase in willingness to share data over 4 years to 2014:

Statements (1= disagree strongly, 5=agree strongly)	2009/2010 n=1329 (median)	2013/2014 n=1015 (median)	P-value
I would be willing to place at least some of my data into a central repository with no restrictions	4.06	4.29	0.001
I would be willing to place all of my data into a central repository with no restrictions	2.98	3.23	0.001
Data may be misinterpreted due to complexity of the data	3.96	4.12	0.001
Data may be used other ways than intended	3.97	4.21	0.001
I share my data with others	3.96	4.06	0.009

Increase of willingness to share data but also more concerned about risks

*Tenoir et al., PLOS One, 2015; 10:e0134826

DataOne Survey: multinational sample of scientific researchers

The attitudes among other stakeholders towards the sharing of IPD from clinical trials have been seen as becoming increasingly positive. A survey in 2019 of Italian patient and citizen groups⁶ found that “Half the respondents were aware of the debate. Those who had an official position were mainly in favour of IPD sharing. Many supported broad access, asking for conditions important for building trust in entities that handle IPD sharing.”

Since 2015 ClinicalTrials.gov enables all clinical trial researchers to detail whether they plan to share IPD and what IPD is available.

A study was carried out analysing these responses for studies registered from January 2016 to August 2017¹⁰. It was found that 36.2% of 25,551 trial records either intended to make IPD available for sharing or were undecided. It was noted that there was evidence of poor general understanding of what was meant by IPD sharing.

ClinicalTrials.gov	Total	NIH	Industry	Other
Interventional studies, registered 1/2016 - 8/2017, high volume registrants (>10) - Response	20842	1151	3738	15953
Plan to share IPD	67%	45%	40%	75%
	5%	11%	0%	6%

Fields in Clinicaltrials.gov (since 12/2015):

- Plan to share IPD (generally provided at study initiation)

- Available IPD/information type (generally provided after study completion)

*Bergeris et al., JAMA, 2018; 319:406

The trajectory of attitudes and behaviour strongly indicates that there will be an increasing requirement for repositories to store and to make available clinical trial data at the individual participant level.

Extent of use of IPD by data users

It takes considerable time to conduct analyses based upon IPD. So far there is limited evidence of significant numbers of IPD meta-analyses. In 2018 it was reported that only 12 IPD meta-analyses were included among 174 proposals to the Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews (CDSR)¹¹.

However, analysis of the number of published systematic IPD metaanalyses indicates that, despite the low ratio, the numbers have been on a steep upward trajectory since 1994.

Costs of storing and using IPD

The costs of submitting IPD to a repository, and of storing it, are considered in the cost modelling for IPD repositories later in the document. However, the additional costs associated with IPD are significant, although difficult to accurately determine.

The paper “Resource implications of preparing individual participant data from a clinical trial to share with external researchers”¹² published in 2017 assessed the activity and resources required to prepare anonymised IPD from clinical trials. For the two trials studied the requirements were 50 and 39.5 hours of staff time and estimated associated costs of £3,185 and £2,540.

The demonstrator was developed with the aims both of storing IPD from clinical trials and of enabling re-analyses, secondary analyses and meta- analyses at the level of individual patient data.

While the quantification of the benefits is difficult, it is clear that the trajectories both for data generators requiring storage of IPD data and for data users making use of such indicate that there will be increasing utility to the use of IPD. The increasing field of potentially valuable applications, with respect to personalised medicine and other fields, makes it appear that there will be increasing need (from generators) and potentially huge utility in terms of users.

Functions and Operations

Type of Operation

In the initial planning two possibilities were considered. Either the repository might be used for storing or analysing clinical trial data from ECRIN trials, or the demonstrator could be developed further into an operational repository for mass data sharing. The former option is not easily practicable due to complexities already described. The latter might feasibly be funded by means of an EOOSC-Life Open Call.

A further significant issue to be addressed is the utility of potentially duplicating resources or services provided by other parties, for example Vivli in respect of the scale of the potential project and University College of London Research Data Repository (RDR) as a repository developed which has plans to interact with the European Open Science Cloud (it is, however, not clear how Brexit may affect any future relationship). Further consideration should be given to how the operational repository would meet important needs that are not and likely will not be met by other parties. Potentially significant issues in assessing this are the difference between pseudonymised and anonymised data, legal problems with EU data being held on servers based in the US, and the particular capacities provided (e.g. with the European Open Science Cloud) that offer unique advantages.

Users

The primary users will be the investigators generating clinical data, for input, storage and analysis, and researchers requesting data for analysis and meta-analysis of data.

Additionally, those users detailed in Section Functions and operations. above could benefit, if it were also to operate as a best practice model.

Services provided

Data storage and archiving for IPD from clinical trials, data sharing, and possible additional services including anonymisation services, protected analysis environments, facilitation of re-analyses, new secondary analyses and meta-analyses.

Other repository services

At the outset of the CORBEL project there were few repositories operating, there are now many more available. Some repositories utilising DSpace include the University of Edinburgh and Biologic Specimen and Data Repository Information Coordinating Center.

Interviews were conducted with three major repositories which deal with clinical trial data (among other issues). The interviews with the repository managers were performed according to a predefined structure, the template for which is given in Appendix 1. The repositories were selected as representatives for an institutional repository (Edinburgh DataShare), funder repository (BioLINCC) and primarily industry repository (Vivli).

These interviews gave insights into costs, funding and operational issues. For reasons of confidentiality specific financial, technical or operational details not publicly available are not reported here but the general outcomes of the interviews are summarised in a structured table (Appendix 2). The key findings inform the assessment and modelling of cost and funding models.

It could be beneficial for different repositories to work together, but there are questions as to whether this is feasible, what it would mean in principle and in practice, and whether it would involve keeping the data and making a distributed analysis or moving the data.

Other Benefits

The operational repository may also be able to provide all the benefits of the best practice model as described above. The assessment of its utility and of the important features for data repositories may be enhanced by the experience of real life operations.

Ownership

The operation of the IT infrastructure and the ownership of the data with all concomitant responsibilities is of key importance. Either the IT infrastructure could be operated within the ECRIN core unit or the operation could be outsourced to another provider.

Aside from the holding of data and the provision of operations, the responsibilities accompanying ownership of the project depend upon the funding body.

Feasibility and Operational Requirements

As quoted earlier, in Tilki B et al², the operational feasibility of the repository is high.

Further operational add-ons may be implemented to deal with further needs, although these may not be available in DSpace and may require additional functionality or even a different program. The Proof of concept of the manageability of such add-ons is demonstrated in the assessment paper cited.

One critical factor is the availability of appropriate expertise and technical competence in adapting and implementing the demonstrator.

Another critical factor is the willingness of the Investigators who provide the data to allow their data to be shared. Moreover, the consent of the parties about / from whom the data is held and the impact of various national and supranational regulations may limit the effective functioning or the scale of the operations.

Many institutions (including ECRIN) and journals (e.g. BMJ) have policies requiring that researchers provide IPD for data sharing. In practice there are many issues which prevent, complicate or delay this process: lack of further incentives for the researchers to do so, lack of consensus and/or understanding as to where or in what format data should be uploaded, time requirements being so broad that 10 years after publication it still may not be required, etc.

Currently ECRIN is performing a scoping review on the impact of data sharing which would allow further analysis and the published protocol is available at <https://osf.io/9gwip>¹.

In addition, the formatting (metadata and schemas) relating to the data is heterogeneous and, as found in the EOSC metadata repository program, the pre-processing required in order to provide standardisation is considerable.

Assessment of Utility as a Sustainable Entity

Before beginning the process of developing an operational repository, it would be best practice to make a survey and analysis of potential users to ascertain the number thereof, and how much benefit this repository would bring in comparison to those systems already existing or likely to be developed.

The users will be of two types:

the data generators who input their results are essential but are hard to incentivise. Even if they are required to submit IPD for data sharing, to do so in a timely fashion and utilising this repository would require incentivisation and facilitation; and the data requestors should be canvassed to determine what advantages they perceive in this repository, their likelihood of participating, and what costs they may be willing to pay, either for access to the data, or for more detailed analysis tools.

This process is outside the scope of the current task or of CORBEL as it would only be important should further actions detailed below lead to a decision to commence the development of operational repository.

Requirements for Sustainability

In order for the repository to function as a sustainable operation, the following are required:

1. Ownership by an operation which has access to the correct technical expertise, data protection safeguards and secure IT systems, which is itself a viable sustainable entity and which is committed to operating the repository for the long term;

¹ <https://osf.io/9gwip>

2. A reliable long-term funding strategy to meet the operational costs;
3. A sufficient number of data generators and data users incentivised to use the operation;
4. Continuing to be useful and state-of-the-art.

Assessment of Costs

Development Cost

Initially there would be the cost of building up and running the IT infrastructure for the repository to be upgraded for real data in terms of personnel and resources. There is little data on specific costs for development of clinical trial data repositories as they are generally quite a recent development. However, the IT infrastructure to be developed in order to operate such repositories (as opposed to the operational costs) is probably akin to the costs of developing the infrastructure for institutional repositories.

In a 2013 paper by Bruns, Lana, Budd¹³, an analysis was performed on the costs academic libraries incur to implement and to manage institutional repositories. They detailed the following result:

Implementation and Annual Reported Costs Plus Annual Reported Costs for Personnel, Software, and Hardware

<i>Costs</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Min</i>	<i>Mdn</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>Max</i>
Implementation	17	\$1,200	\$25,000	\$52,100	\$300,000
Annual	20	\$500	\$31,500	\$77,300	\$275,000
Personnel, Annual	17	\$100	\$70,000	\$86,186	\$235,200
Software, Annual	10	\$2,500	\$23,000	\$22,350	\$40,000
Hardware, Annual	6	\$500	\$5,500	\$13,250	\$50,000

While DSpace is Open Source software, other software costs will be involved in implementation and in creating a secure environment for sensitive data.

An interesting observation from the data above and the three interviews with repositories is that, while development costs performed in-house are hard to determine, they are for most reported cases relatively similar to, or slightly less than, one year's operational costs.

Because in this case the demonstrator has been developed, the costs of development, pre-operations, would mainly involve measures to provide a secure environment for data, to have the client agreements and access agreements developed and to integrate with existing IT infrastructure. These are on-going activities and will continue to be reflected in the operational costs.

As an initial estimate, for the reasons given above, the relevant costs would approximate those of operational costs for a year for the implementation work required.

Operational Costs

The personnel costs will depend upon what services are provided for the user. If users are required to perform de-identification of data themselves, then costs will be not be as high but there may be less user uptake.

It is not possible at this point to make a precise budget for the costs of running the DSpace demonstrator as an operational repository. Factors yet to be determined would have a significant impact, particularly:

1. Will the operation include such activities as assisting the clients with de-identifying data? This would add considerable costs but would also be a sought after service, based upon database user reports;
2. Will the operation include assistance with analysis of the data, perhaps offering this extra service as one for which fees are charged?
3. To what extent will activities additional to the operation of the repository be pursued? Such activities could include communication, analysis of quality criteria, development of forms of quality control or assessment, jointly working with users, providers and regulators on interoperability and FAIR data, working to change the culture on data sharing for clinical trials, etc. These could be very complementary activities but would add considerably to time costs.
4. How many clinical trials will be managed by the repository? It could represent 60, as ECRIN's clinical trials portfolio (assuming all would immediately be ready for inclusion), a significantly greater number such as 400 if utilised across Europe as an integrated element of the European Open Science Cloud. Vivli initiated with 2,500 clinical trials and has expanded that to 4,600 in 2 years, but requires funding in the order of millions of dollars.

Below is a speculative analysis of the major activities consuming labour per year and other anticipated annual costs.

	<u>Fixed Person Hours</u>	<u>Person Hours Per Clinical Trial Submission</u>	<u>Annual Person Hours for 30 Clinical Trials</u>	<u>Annual Person Hours for 400 Clinical Trials</u>	<u>Annual Person Hours for 2,500 Clinical Trials</u>
Ingest					
Generate SIP - supervision, error handling		0,2	6	40	500
Receive Submission		0,2	6	40	500
Quality Assurance	20	0,2	26	60	520
Generate Descriptive Information		0,2	6	40	500
Coordinate Updates	10	0,2	16	50	510
Archival Storage					
Receive Data		0,2	6	40	500
Manage Storage Hierarchy		0,2	6	40	500
Replace Media (labour, fixed costs below)		0,1	3	20	250
Error checking	20	0,5	35	120	1.270
Disaster recovery	20	0,2	26	60	520
Provide data		0,5	15	100	1.250
Data Management					
Administer database	80		80	80	80
Perform queries		1	30	200	2.500
Generate reports	25	0,3	34	85	775
Receive database updates	30		30	30	30
Administration					
Negotiate Submission Agreement		1	30	200	2.500
Manage System Configuration	30		30	30	30
Archival Information Update	40		40	40	40
Physical Access Control	20		20	20	20
Establish Standards and Policies	40		40	40	40
Audit Submission		0,2	6	40	500
Activate Requests		2	60	400	5.000
Customer service	20	2	80	420	5.020
Preservation Planning					
Monitor Designated Community	10	0,1	13	30	260
Monitor Technology	10		10	10	10
Develop Preservation Strategies and Standards	20		20	20	20
Develop Packaging Designs and Migration Plans	12		12	12	12
Access					
Coordinate access activities (Data Access Committee)	40	0,2	46	80	540
Generate DIP		0,2	6	40	500
Deliver response		0,2	6	40	500
Related Activities					
Analysing and enhancing systems	20		20	20	20
Training and education	30		30	30	30
Communication and dissemination	30		30	30	30
Strategic planning and review	20		20	20	20
Legal counsel	40	1	70	240	2.540
Total person hours			914	2.767	27.837
Estimated labour cost at a blended rate of E60 per hour			€ 54.840	€ 166.020	€ 1.670.220
Additional Costs					
Insurance (in addition to company's existing cyber insurance)			€ 10.000	€ 20.000	€ 40.000
Auditing and certification procedures			€ 2.000	€ 4.000	€ 8.000
Hardware costs			€ 5.000	€ 10.000	€ 250.000
Software costs (Open Source for repository)			€ 10.000	€ 15.000	€ 30.000
Total Estimated Costs			€ 81.840	€ 215.020	€ 1.998.220

Analysis of the key cost areas

Ingest

The Submission Information Package (SIP) is the information package that is delivered to the repository (the data / metadata provided to the repository by the data provider). The costs associated with this procedure are very dependent upon the degree to which the data provider is assisted in the process of submitting the data within an appropriate format.

The demonstrator has been assessed as capable of supporting a range of file types and allows the upload of different metadata schema in addition to the default Dublin Core schema. The mechanisms and guidelines for the upload of files were also positively assessed. These factors should make the process easier, but it is still not a straightforward process and is likely to involve administrator assistance at times.

The work on producing the guidelines and procedures for the uploads will have taken place in the development stage and will only require regular review and updating.

One feature of the quality for repositories for IPD from clinical trials identified in Banzi et al. (2019)⁵ is that the repository should include de-identification practices before upload. The pilot demonstrates the requirement to provide links to de-identification tools and requirements and to provide guidelines.

In practice very few, if any, repositories offer full de-identification practices and it was recognised in D3.3.3. that this may be an overly demanding criterion as a necessary quality feature. A lesser requirement, that of providing links to de-identification services, is a more usual and achievable function.

The checking of the de-identification process is one that will require labour and expertise. If the decision is made either to implement additional modules to facilitate this process, or to provide active assistance and consultancy to the users, then this may be a significantly greater cost area.

Access

It may be necessary to establish a Data Access Committee (DAC) - a registered body of one or more people responsible for data release to external requestors based on consent and/or National Research Ethics terms.

However, based upon the interviews with other repositories for clinical trial data, a formal DAC is not necessarily required— for two of the three repositories with which interviews were conducted there were no formal DACs or Data Access Board established.

Related Activities

Many of these activities are not an essential part of the operation of the repository but are complementary activities that, as discussed earlier, would significantly enhance the utility of the development and running of the operational repository.

There are basic legal costs related to drawing up service and confidentiality contracts and to advising on data protection and management laws and regulations, which should be factored into any project plan. In situations where the repository is operating with data providers or data users outside the EU, or using detailed IPD which is theoretically traceable, more extensive legal expertise may be required.

Costing of the Person Hours

A full budget would involve an estimated distribution of the person hours for different activities to people on different salary levels. Many of the activities will require involvement from people with highly sought after and well-paid expertise, in technical design, data management or analysis, or legal expertise. Some of the activities may be allocated to people on lower salaries. This could best be assessed by reference to the organisation's plans for respective participants in the project, their expected contribution and general remuneration rate.

Additional Costs

Certification procedures may be integrated with the development of a qualification or a form of certification.

An alternative to running the IT infrastructure within the ECRIN core unit would be to outsource the operation of the repository to a third party.

The costs of running a system that enables re-analyses of clinical trials, secondary analyses, and meta-analyses at the patient level needs to be considered as set against the costs of doing so using aggregated data.

IPD offers advantages and, when feasible, should be considered the best opportunity to summarise the results of multiple studies. However, the resources, time and cooperation required for such studies will continue to limit their use in many important areas of clinical medicine which can be meaningfully and cost-effectively approached by properly performed APD meta-analyses. As shown by Lyman & Kuderer¹⁴, APD meta-analyses continue to be the mainstay of systematic reviews utilized by the US Preventive Services Task Force, the Cochrane Collaboration and many professional societies to support clinical practice guidelines.

Assessment of Funding Sources

Funding for development

If the repository is developed within EOSC-Life, then funding may be pursued through an Open Call. The basic EOSC-Life budget for ECRIN, who are likely principal developers, is 11 person months, many of which can already be assigned to different tasks within the project.

From literature review, discussions with other repositories, and the expertise from the development of the pilot repository, this level of resources would probably be insufficient for the development, implementation and data input desired for an operational open access repository.

Funding from an Open Call in EOSC-Life may be available to partially cover the development and implementation of the operational repository, but would not standardly extend to cover maintenance and further upgrading as a sustainable entity.

In addition, there have not been discussions on this issue with EOSC-Life and it has been recorded that at least one data repository, RDR at UCL, had plans to be the repository that interacts with the European Open Science Cloud. In view of Brexit and other events these plans may have been changed but information on this is not readily available

Funding for operations

There are three potential sources for funding/support to maintain the operation:

1. User fees/member fees/contributions. For the purposes of this paper it is not considered that the repository will be utilised on a for-profit basis. Those investigators inputting IPD standardly are doing so for it to be publicly available as a general good. In this area a for-profit operation would be unlikely to be considered a viable option.

However, it is not unreasonable to cover some of the costs of the operation either by user fees or membership fees. The former could be specifically targeted at e.g. industry or private enterprise bodies. The latter, a more likely alternative, could be a payment towards costs from those who use the service for prolonged periods or who wish to utilise further analysis tools or access expert advice. Another potential source is not to charge fees but to solicit voluntary contributions from users towards running the service.

In the case of Vivli, in 2018 14% of their revenues came from membership contributions and this ratio may well increase to cover more and more of the costs. Analyses of existing repositories indicate that commonly between 5-33% of operational costs are covered by such revenues. It is not unreasonable to plan for a similar level of income to defray costs, but it is unlikely to account for more than a quarter of the required funding.

2. Support from ECRIN, in terms of person months, resources and financing.
ECRIN may be willing to provide the person power, resources and financing as required on the basis that this is a core part of their operations. The Governing Board could consider and may approve such a long-term commitment, but it would represent a very substantial cost burden if there were no other sources of support.
3. Long-term commitment to financial support, either from philanthropic bodies or as a foundation.

Given the costs associated with maintaining the sustainable entity, the preference of funders for development rather than maintenance, the apparently similar projects being supported, and the very long-term nature of required commitments, this would be difficult to obtain. Key factors in seeking such funding would be to demonstrate the significant utility of the repository, to prove its feasibility, and to begin seeking interest from the start of the project. A foundation established for the purposes of running a long-term repository is technically possible if donor(s) could be persuaded, but there would need to be a very strong case made.

Assessment of Risk Factors and Mitigating Measures

Duplication of services that already exist or that are to be developed, for example with Vivli's global remit and ambitions

Risk level: High

Likely impact: Severe

Mitigating measures: Assess what important needs will be addressed that are not currently addressed and are not likely to be in the near future, bearing in mind that this is an area that has seen enormous expansion and development in the last few years.

Examples include:

- Problems with differences in data protection legislation between US and EU;
- The use of pseudonymised data may be offered, while Vivli only uses anonymised data. The potential added utility of such a service and likely uptake should be examined, perhaps with an informal or formal survey of possible users;
- Functionalities offered that Vivli do not provide;

- Potential concerns about lack of diversity in the available repositories. Such concerns have, in fact, been raised regarding Vivli, with T. Groves, editor of BMJ Open describing it thus: “It seems simply too monolithic, too rigid, too focused on one study type, too commercial (potentially), and too U.S.-focused. The real life solution is almost certainly going to be an ecosystem of platforms that learn, over time, to talk to each other.”

Technological developments requiring major upgrades or maintenance work to keep the repository operational

Risk level: Moderate to Low

Likely impact: Moderate

Mitigating measures: The choice of DSpace as a platform already goes some way towards mitigating the risk of major maintenance work and the need for major upgrades for the proposed repository. DSpace is an open source software package designed for the creation of open access repositories created by MIT and HP Labs. It was made with the specific aim of long-term document storage. It is used in conjunction with a relational database. This database structure has been in use since the 1970s and is extremely widely used. It is very unlikely that relational databases will go out of fashion or become impossible to maintain.

That said, there is always the possibility of maintenance work being required by people adept at working with relational databases, which may prove expensive if done by contractors, expensive in terms of person time if done by ECRIN staff members.

Sustainability of DSpace as Open Access software

Risk level: Very Low

Likely impact: Severe

Mitigating measures: DSpace is a widely used tool for building repositories, with over 2,500 repositories making use of it, according to its registry². The company it is now run by, DuraSpace, recently merged with Lyris, a non-profit with the aim of providing enduring access to academic, cultural and scientific knowledge. It is unlikely that the platform will suddenly cease to exist, given the number of organisations invested in its continued use.

In the event that the interface were no longer maintained, it would still be possible to create one that could access the repository database, although this would require expensive development work.

Failure to secure long term funding or support to continue to operate as a sustainable output

Risk level: Moderate

Likely impact: Severe

Mitigating Measures: Early activity both to identify continued support opportunities, to communicate with possible funders and to prove and demonstrate the value of the operation.

² <https://duraspace.org/registry>

SWOT Analysis

Utilisation of the Developed Demonstrator Repository for storing and analysing clinical trial data, either that of ECRIN or of others

<p style="text-align: center;">STRENGTHS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrator repository already developed with good assessment of functionality and utility. • Closely linked to ECRIN's core activities and to researchers working with ECRIN. • Operational control by ECRIN of trial data, not reliant on third parties. 	<p style="text-align: center;">WEAKNESSES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moderately high fixed costs. • Without further development does not offer state-of-the-art functionalities to data generators or users. • Represents a very long-term commitment in terms of time, resources and regulation.
<p style="text-align: center;">OPPORTUNITIES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rapidly expanding environment of researchers both obliged and motivated to store and share clinical trial data and of usage of such data. • In-house further development possible based upon future needs and wants. • Can be used as data for further work on the technical and theoretical aspects of data storage and usage. 	<p style="text-align: center;">THREATS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other repositories are available, potential redundancy if identical services offered elsewhere. • Requires buy-in by trial sponsors. • As fixed costs are so high, may be unreasonably expensive on a per trial / use basis with only a small population of users.

Development of the demonstrator into a state-of-the-art operational repository for mass data sharing, perhaps in conjunction with EOOSC-Life

<p style="text-align: center;">STRENGTHS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrator repository already developed. • Strong complementarities with ECRIN's core activities and with plans such as developing data seals of approval. • In house expertise and enthusiasm. • Serves real need in Europe. 	<p style="text-align: center;">WEAKNESSES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reluctance to share trial data – difficulties in obtaining input. • Represents a very long-term commitment in terms of time, resources and regulation. • Very high set-up and operational costs. • Unclear revenue model.
<p style="text-align: center;">OPPORTUNITIES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding for development may be available through EOOSC-Life. • Increasing requirements for and acceptance of value of clinical data sharing. • Over time, cost of depositing can be included as eligible cost in <u>sponsors' grant applications</u> 	<p style="text-align: center;">THREATS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other repositories are available, with <u>Vivli</u>, <u>particular</u> having a very wide remit and ambition and other repositories developed with plans to be the repository to interact with EOOSC. • Funding for development not sufficient and certainly no resources from EOOSC-Life for maintenance. • Very challenging environment to secure long-term funding / support. • Very complex regulatory environment.

Repository Support Service (Option 4)

Functions and Operations

Users and Services Offered

Building upon and following on from the work on the creation of and assessment of the demonstrator, ECRIN could develop, offer and run a costed repository support service, specialising in sensitive data based upon Figshare. This could offer such services as metadata creation, de-identification, documentation, initial request review, etc.

Such a service could be offered from the start to sponsors of ECRIN supported trials, but it could also be attractive to a much wider group of researchers, given the likely increased pressure for making IPD available.

This could lead to other complementary/associated services being developed or further developed and being made more widely available such as information on best practices, which would be used by data generators and users as well as repository management and academia.

In running such a service, ECRIN would both be motivated to, and have more information and experience increasing their ability to, develop a suite of SOPs and related documents that had been discussed internally as being necessary for the responsible management of repositories.

They would be able to test and improve these in the real world and to provide examples of use as well as evidence of effectiveness or otherwise and more knowledge about implementation and likely issues arising.

These SOPs, related documents, findings, and any research proceeding from or drawing upon this work could be disseminated from the ECRIN web site, potentially sharing best practices and information with all interested parties who would then be users.

Costs

Figshare is an online open access repository. It is free to upload content and free to access, in adherence to the principle of open data. Figshare removes the need for the institution to build and fund its own IT infrastructure to support a repository. The significant costs associated with implementing and utilising the platform, are related to staff time and will be analogous to those discussed in the cost analysis for repositories above.

Other providers of these services and associated resources/costing

Few, if any repositories perform de-identification processes themselves, although the interviews performed established that they had to perform a lot of work checking, verifying and seeking amendments to the de-identification processes performed by the data generators. Estimates of costs for third parties to perform de-identification services were in the range of 2-5,000 Euros although variable dependent upon the quantity and complexity of the data.

In the paper "Resource implications of preparing individual participant data from a clinical trial to share with external researchers"¹², an assessment was made of the resource requirements for preparing anonymised IPD for sharing, from two publicly funded clinical trials.

The process of preparing a dataset and documentation ready for sharing for the two trials took around 50 hours and 39.5 hours at total costs of £3,185 and £2,540 respectively.

In addition to the savings in terms of resources or third party billing, a more expert process would greatly aid the repository staff who have noted that they spend a lot of resources and tie in dealing with problems arising from incorrectly prepared datasets.

It is possible that the required resources, costings and ease of facilitation of anonymisation services may decrease substantially in the future with the development of better automated anonymisation methods or tools, but this is hard to predict. Such developments would reduce the difficulty and costs for other parties, but would also make it easier to provide these services, so the decrease to expected fees for services would likely be offset by decreased costs.

Other Benefits

This could greatly increase the credibility of ECRIN as an organisation that understood repositories for sensitive data.

It would give ECRIN much more leverage when talking to other repositories (e.g. Vivli), for example discussing ways to harmonise metadata or application procedures.

It would also assist greatly with any attempt to develop and/or integrate quality criteria for such repositories.

Figshare (www.figshare.com) is an online digital repository of research data (digital data, figures, images, videos, etc.). The company allows data citation and has partnered with ORCID.

Ownership

ECRIN may or may not want to manage its own local storage, but Figshare at least provides the option, and initially leaving Figshare to handle the infrastructure would allow services to be developed much more quickly. DSpace, although it claims greater usage numbers, is always a locally managed system. Figshare can also offer DOI minting, which may become increasingly important.

As always, viability will depend on estimated costs and income.

The operation of the IT infrastructure and the ownership of the data with all concomitant responsibilities is of key importance. Either the IT infrastructure could be operated within the ECRIN core unit or the operation could be outsourced to another provider.

As regards the responsibilities that go with owning the project, apart from the holding of the data and the provision of operations that depends upon the funding body.

Feasibility and Operational Requirements

Discussions with repositories (Vivli, BioLINCC and Edinburgh University) and literature reviews indicate that most data generators either require contracted third party assistance or else incur significant costs in terms of time and resources. As the requirements for IPD data submission are becoming more and more widespread, the market is large and growing. Beyond the initial development, there would be few fixed costs, so that sustainability would not be hard to secure.

SWOT Analysis

<p style="text-align: center;">STRENGTHS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complementary with development of SOPs and related documents. • Simple setup and operational costs and structure. • ECRIN has access to broad user base through own users, EOSC and other infrastructure initiatives. • Supports real need in user community. 	<p style="text-align: center;">WEAKNESSES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of visibility as a service provider. • Lack of marketing budget • New type of service may take time to get market recognition.
<p style="text-align: center;">OPPORTUNITIES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Could greatly increase the credibility of ECRIN as understanding repositories for sensitive data. • More leverage when talking to other repositories (e.g. <u>Vivli</u>), for example discussing ways to <u>harmonise</u> metadata or application procedures. • Could assist greatly with any attempt to develop and / or integrate quality criteria for such repositories. 	<p style="text-align: center;">THREATS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential conflict of interest if both service provider and accreditor. • Other service providers with more recognition.

Development in the context of a model for future rapid response framework for health emergency readiness (Option 5)

COVID-19 Implications and Response

Since early 2020 Europe has been experiencing a public health crisis unprecedented in modern European history. As thousands of European citizens are infected with the SARS-CoV-2 every day and the number of casualties is increasing rapidly, Europe needs a coordinated effort to advance scientific understanding of the virus and its effect on patients, and resources to fight the pandemic.

ESFRI has made clear that the European RIs have a vital role to play in supporting the science-led response to the COVID-19 outbreak. This ESFRI initiative feeds into a larger set of coordinated R&I actions at EU level presented in the ERA vs. Corona Action Plan. The Action Plan sets out key measures to coordinate, share and increase support for R&I. In particular, for Research Infrastructures, funds are being added and re-oriented to support RI projects providing services and activities in response to the Coronavirus outbreak. In order to share research data, a European data exchange platform for Coronavirus is also being established in the framework of the European Open Science Cloud.

Benefits of a data repository for IPD from clinical trials

With the COVID crisis it is necessary to build a clinical trial data-sharing repository for COVID trials in the context of the European COVID-19 research data platform (led by EBI/ELIXIR). The experience from this project and the results summarised in this deliverable could be of enormous value for the planned research data platform, due to the enormously fragmented nature of current research into the virus and potential therapies and vaccines.

This is clearly demonstrated by the fact that as of mid April 2020, in the months since COVID-19 has spread, researchers have launched more than 180 clinical trials of everything from repurposed antivirals and immunomodulators to unproven cell therapies and vitamin C. A further 150 trials are preparing to recruit patients¹⁴.

The increasing level of requirement to share and positive attitudes towards sharing IPD from clinical trials has been detailed elsewhere, but in this case it is clear that both the requirements from institutions and the attitudes towards the value of this are much greater. European institutions such as Inserm, UNIMED – Mediterranean Universities Union, the European University Association, among others have signed the Wellcome Trust's Statement on Data Sharing in Public Health Emergencies agreeing to put all relevant COVID-19 research to open access, make research findings available before peer review, share interim and final research data on the outbreak and to share them with the World Health Organisation. In addition, currently the Research Data Alliance (RDA) COVID-19 Working Group is developing policies and guidelines for data sharing in the COVID-19 crisis.³

Research infrastructures involved in building the EOSC have also opened up access to their data on COVID-19 such as CERIC ERIC, and EMBL-EBI among others.

An EU clinical trial IPD repository as part of the research data platform, following the rules of GDPR and associated legislation, could be very important for all the reasons described above relating to the value of IPD, particularly given the scale and urgency of this crisis.

Other potential providers and collaborators

The repositories such as Vivli or BioLINCC are not currently equipped to handle EU data with GDPR compliance (ref) and other university or industry repositories are targeted at specific sets of researchers or indications, not appropriate for this task.

Europe's open science cloud is expected to become a virtual ecosystem that will be linking all scientific disciplines and sectors. From a technological standpoint, the EOSC is expected to provide the tools for such collaboration.

The future European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) could be a vital tool for (1) opening up scientific data on the virus, (2) sharing live on-the-ground data on the spread of the virus, and (3) accessing and combining this data not only to eradicate the virus but learn how to deal with similar viruses and future outbreaks and be the answer to societal challenges as they emerge.

ELIXIR Director Niklas Blomberg coordinates the EOSC-Life project, one of the EOSC projects accelerating open science through open data, open reproducible tools and workflows in the life sciences field. ELIXIR-Belgium and de.NBI/ELIXIR-Germany are the ELIXIR nodes involved in the latest activities towards COVID-19. Blomberg said open science helps researchers to act quickly and efficiently.

In addition to the opportunities offered by EOSC and EOSC-Life, ECRIN has recognised the importance of sharing research data among researchers worldwide and has established a COVID-19 Taskforce with its national partners with the following aims (ref):

³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-covid19>

1. Review and digest the scientific literature on COVID clinical trials
2. Develop a metadata repository for COVID trials making all the non-sensitive COVID-19 trial data accessible
3. Develop a database on the regulatory, ethical and data protection fast track approvals across all European countries
4. Ensure preparedness of its national clinical trial unit (CTU) partners for COVID trials
5. Combine and coordinate national initiatives to promote multinational rather than national trials, including through connection with national funders, sponsors investigators and CTUs
6. Develop partnership with national and pan-European investigation networks on infectious diseases and intensive care
7. Outreach to investigators, sponsors, patients, policymakers, funders, and citizens
8. International cooperation and outreach, including with WHO and through CRIGH and other initiatives

The requirement (2) expressly relates to the proposed project and the other requirements are very complementary. Within this framework there is a clear need and an ideal opportunity for establishing such an operational repository.

Funding (Requirements and potential funding)

A huge proportion of the active and planned trials are or will be based in the EU and it is probable that the number of trials will continue to increase rapidly. While not all will have appropriate interoperable IPD that would be input into the repository, it is reasonable to assume required capacity for 400 clinical trials, while allowing for the high possibility that there may be many more that could be usefully accommodated.

There is possible utility in including clinical trial data from other trials not specifically related to COVID-19 but to other coronaviruses, respiratory illnesses and/or viral spreading. However, the efforts to get such data also input would mean this would not be a priority yet could be provisionally added to a greater or lesser extent to increase utility.

Based upon the modelling in the Section Assessment of Costs above, for 400 clinical trials the estimated annual operating costs would be in the region of 200,000 Euros and the set up costs also in the region of 200,000 Euros.

By offering services such as de-identification and support services as described in section 4, investigators will be incentivised to utilise this platform and the successful use of data would be expedited.

As detailed above, this would increase the projected operating costs by a factor of around 15 to 20 per cent, likely to be covered by the funding body.

As regards revenue models, in this case the entirety of the funding would be from grants or national bodies and it may even be appropriate to offer the additional services free of charge to researchers in order to incentivise and accelerate accurate data input.

As of early 2020 there are active or imminent funding opportunities to the level of billions of euros to address research related to COVID-19.

The European Commission in late January launched a €10 million call under Horizon 2020 for funding research specifically into coronavirus. Many other sources of EU and national funding for initiatives is been generated.

Funding beyond EU and member states include Wellcome Trust, CEPI (CEPI.net) and The Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation, all of which will offer huge resources for funding into preparedness and COVID with multi-sourced funding vehicles.

Immediate funding for set-up costs and operations would be best secured by applying as a project with beneficiaries – probably as a public-private consortium.

The other revenue streams discussed in relation to repositories, such as fees for services or membership, are much less immediate and likely to be precluded by the initial funding requirements.

Major issues

a. Lack of interoperability is both a problem and opportunity

Without a minimum level of interoperability of IPD, there may be less utility to the repository, and this is very likely to be an issue with so many disparate trials. However, in the context of the ECRIN Task Force and the AMRI aims, the operation would include advice on, lobbying for and awareness raising about the best way of classifying and utilising metadata across trials to facilitate this. The creation and operation of the repository will provide invaluable evidence for and impetus for broader agreement on best practice and minimal requirements to maximise interoperability of data. This would be particularly important if the designed system, protocols and services are also used as a model for or part of a future rapid response framework for health emergency readiness, as well as part of a body to advise on and help to ensure interoperability.

b. Clarity required on the permissibility of cross border sharing of pseudonymised data

There are significant potential barriers to cross-border sharing of IPD from clinical trials, as even pseudonymised data may in principle alone be sufficient to permit identification. There are various potential means to deal with this, including the use of hash keys and confounding data, but the permissibility of such in the context of GDPR is still unclear and researchers and sponsors may be reluctant to broach this area.

If protocols, agreements and wider education on this area were considered a complementary activity, in conjunction with the ECRIN COVID Task Force and other parties, then this activity and the resulting legal, educational and practical resources would be a valuable constituent of a future rapid response framework for health emergency readiness.

c. Long-term utility of meta-analyses or use of IPD

While measures are being taken to expedite clinical trials in this area and there will be major efforts to incentivise early input of data, it will be a matter of years until data users are in a good position to utilise the repository to carry out meta-analyses and other operations.

If an effective vaccine has been established or the COVID-19 pandemic has otherwise subsided, there would be much less need for the data and services associated with the repository. It is impossible to accurately predict the likelihood of this and so the level of the long-term utility is largely dependent upon an unknown factor.

However, if it is envisaged that this repository and associated resources and services be established as a model for future rapid responses to unknown or poorly understood pathogens, then the long-term utility would be well established even in the case where the level of interest in and research into COVID-19 diminishes considerably.

Sustainability

As regards sustainability, such a repository would face particular challenges that may arise from the facts that:

1. There is currently a huge focus on and funding bodies looking at tackling COVID19, but this cannot be reasonably anticipated to be the same in several years' time; and
2. There are currently a huge number of clinical trials in the area, but this also does not mean that the same will be the case in future years.

It is unlikely that a very long term funding commitment would be made as the urgency of the data sharing is very much time bound. However, there is likely to remain a very strong correlation between funding interest and the number of clinical trials, so that the operation could be scaled down in the future to run at lower costs for fewer trials. Should the funding for maintaining the repository for data access become difficult in future years, a transfer of data may be possible, but these costs are much more modest, around 30,000 Euros per year depending upon data users, and could in future be partially supported by services offered to data users, as per the plans for other repositories. These alternative revenue models are not appropriate in the current moment but many be envisaged as a possible solution to long-term sustainability when the situation is much less critical.

Conclusion - Development in the context of a model for future rapid response framework for health emergency readiness.

Based upon the above considerations, the most effective and important long-term deliverable would be the immediate development of the repository in the context of a model for future rapid response framework for health emergency readiness. This model would include services, protocols and legal frameworks established to facilitate rapid re-use of the system.

In addition to the immediate crisis presented by COVID-19, there is a significant need for a functional model for a data repository, protocols, services and cultural impact to enable the rapid and effective use of clinical trial data relating to any unknown or poorly known pathogen with urgent public health impact. Such a model would have superior long term sustainability, would be able to be further developed and ameliorated based upon the experiences of the project as it relates to COVID-19 data, and would also address all of the needs identified. In conjunction with the initiatives of the ECRIN COVID task force, AMRI (ref. statement), EOSC-Life and others, this would be an invaluable resource.

The initial repository set-up and operational costs would initially be as described above and would potentially increase only in the case of a new public health emergency, in which case additional appropriate funding could be expected to be available.

This situation would also avoid duplication of work and allow much quicker response in addressing any future scenarios.

The repository could become part of a future rapid response framework for health emergency readiness. It will serve as a vital part of body to advise on and help to ensure interoperability and a key

part of the scientific community's experience for addressing poorly understood or unknown pathogens in critical situations.

The project best delivered would not only be about establishing an enterprise in a functioning environment, but expediting the culture change required to make the enterprise viable and useful. The best enterprise therefore is not just the vital and integral COVID-19 response, but also developing a structure and mechanisms to address any unforeseen pathogen related public health emergency.

SWOT Analysis

<p style="text-align: center;">STRENGTHS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential to improve COVID-19 response • Established repository system, expertise available and cooperative collaborators • Potential to enable and facilitate rapid response to future health crises 	<p style="text-align: center;">WEAKNESSES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cross-border data sharing concerns • Issues with interoperability of underlying data • The time-lag before IPD clinical data utility – time to operational readiness • Very volatile demand requiring flexibility of scale and operations
<p style="text-align: center;">OPPORTUNITIES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enormous funding opportunities relating to COVID-19 crisis • Landscape more amenable to culture change due to crisis • Opportunity to develop answers to data sharing and data interoperability issues in a broad framework • Good case for future funding for preventative measures 	<p style="text-align: center;">THREATS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal issues – privacy and security requirements • Failure to get sufficient buy-in – data users, data generators and culture in general • Very volatile long-term funding • Very fast changing landscape

Next steps

In order to proceed with the development of the project discussions should be held with EOSC-Life, the ECRIN COVID Task Force, AMRI and other potential public and private partners to get consensus on the desirability of and willingness to cooperate on the project.

When provisional consensus on the elements to be included in the project and respective contributions is established then the following actions should be concurrently executed immediately:

1. Application for appropriate funding as offered by EU, National or other bodies (ref. announcement 4 May) as a project with beneficiaries – one option could be a public-private consortium;

2. Advanced feasibility study – assembly of a panel of experts to assess how and whether this can be financed, set up and utilised;
3. Draw up an implementation plan in order to elucidate the steps around funding, design, construction and operations with particular emphasis on resolving the major issues detailed in

Assemble a relevant panel of experts to assess whether this can be Financed, set up and utilised.

Set up an enterprise plan in order to elucidate the precise next steps around funding, design, construction and operations with particular emphasis on resolving the caveats detailed in Section Major issues (interoperability, cross-border sharing and long-term utility).

Options for ownership, governance, alternative revenue sources would be secondary questions to be addressed - while options for ownership are numerous, the sensitivity of the data places limitations on the ownership and this will be analysed.

Conclusions

This report examines various options for building upon the work done by ECRIN in developing a demonstrator repository for clinical trial data. Five different possibilities are considered, with a view to making recommendations as to next steps to follow on from this work.

Option 1

The sharing of best practice regarding repositories for such data based on lessons learned during the project is recommended, being potentially of significant benefit to those who develop and manage repositories and also to the wider community of repository users. Those who worked on the project could fairly easily put together documentation to this effect, this would require no further funding (although the cost of person hours to the organisations involved should be taken into consideration), and the potential impact could be wide-reaching.

Options 2 and 3

The possibility of developing the demonstrator repository into an operational repository containing data provided by ECRIN and possibly others is considered to be too problematic to be feasible in the near future. However, the development of a state-of-the-art mass data sharing repository is a possibility, albeit one that would require the pursuit of designated funding for a large-scale project. An EOSC-Life open call would be one potential avenue to pursue for such funding, but there are also other possibilities.

Currently there is no convincing strategy to secure this and so it is not a viable route at the moment.

Option 4

The fourth option considered is the possibility of ECRIN running a costed repository service, based on Figshare and offering additional services such as metadata creation, documentation, and de-identification of data (which was flagged in interviews as something that varies greatly in terms of quality between datasets submitted). This would complement the first option, the one of developing best practice guidelines and quality certification for repositories.

The fourth option would build upon the work performed in the first option. It would require modest capital outlay in developing the Figshare application but the other costs would be variable and

discretionary depending upon the demand. Analysis indicates that the services would be useful, in demand, and economically viable. Further developments such as certifications or more comprehensive methods of advice and best practice guides could be implemented based upon the initial service provision. This option, if funding for development is available, could be pursued. However, many of the support services could be included in a complementary way with the enactment of Option 5.

Option 5

The fifth option, offering the most effective and important long-term deliverable, involves be the immediate development of the repository in the context of a model for future rapid response framework for health emergency readiness. This model would include services, protocols and legal frameworks established to facilitate rapid re-use of the system. Given the positive environment with funders and potential collaborators it is recommended that this be pursued. The proposed next steps are detailed in section above.

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Abbreviations

- CORBEL	Coordinated Research Infrastructures Building Enduring Life-science Services
- DAC	Data Access Committee
- EATRIS	European Infrastructure for Translational Medicine
- ECRIN	European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network
- EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
- EU	European Union
- IPD	Individual Participant Data
- RDR	University College of London Research Data Repository
- UCL	University College London
- WHO	World Health Organisation

Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed:

Yes

Adjustments made

The outcomes of subtask 3.3.4 were helping the group defining the specifications for potential data services to be exposed to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC); therefore it had been agreed with the PO to allow three additional months to coordinate and gather information from the new EOSC-Life project.

Appendices

Appendix 1: Questionnaire

Questionnaire used as basis for repository interviews:

CORBEL Task 3.3.4.

Questionnaire about Repository Costs, Funding and Operations

Question 1: General Repository Information

- What types of data are held in the repository?
- What types of data other than clinical trial data?

Question 2: Funding

- What types of funding – public, private, user-based, etc. are used?
 - Are the funding sources and splits different for the development stage and the maintenance / operation stage?

Question 3: Legal Advice

- How is this handled? In-house staff or outsourced?
- What was the major requirement for legal advice?

Question 4: Metrics for Data Access Committee

- How many people are involved? Who are they? What are their costs and conditions?
- How are they selected? How often do they meet?
- How much review is required (per request)?

Question 5: General Sustainability Considerations

- For how long is funding secured / reliably anticipated?
- Are there alternative plans in place to ensure sustainability?

Question 6: Services provided (in addition to basic repository function)

- Are any separate services provided to data providers or data users?
 - (e.g. de-identification services, protected analysis environment)
- Can the costs be approximately split between the costs for basic infrastructure and the costs for basic services?

Question 7: Costs

- What were the major costs in developing the repository?
 - e.g. human costs, licences, technical costs/
- What is the approximate split of costs between:
 - Software costs, technical costs, legal and admin costs?
- What functions, if any, are or were outsourced?
- Are there any other significant constituent cost areas?

Appendix 2: Summary of interviews with Repositories

Question 1: General Repository Information

- What types of data are held in the repository?
- What types of data are held other than clinical trial data?

University of Edinburgh

- A more general purpose academic repository. They take data sets from all the schools and colleges in Edinburgh university – almost every discipline.
- The depositors are Edinburgh University researchers or collaborators.
- One exception – when the repository became the destination for a repository which was shutting down, ShareGeo, which was a national repository that took data sets from academics around the UK.
- They provide open access with some caveats. Anyone in the world may be using it.
- There are also clinical trial data - including one deposited earlier on from World Stroke Trial. It is Open Access.
- There are also some newer data sets from clinical trial units and others from the Medical School that have restricted access.

Vivli

- It is mostly clinical trials data held in the repository.
- Other than clinical trial data, the repository holds observational data, genomics data, real world data (all human data, not translational).

BioLINCC

- The NHLBI has supported data collection from participants in epidemiology studies and clinical trials for over six decades.
- These data have often been sent to the NHLBI at the conclusion of the study and placed in the Data Repository.
- The Data Repository is managed by the Epidemiology Branch in the Division of Cardiovascular Sciences and includes individual level data on hundreds of thousands of participants from more than 145 Institute-supported clinical trials and observational studies.

Question 2: Funding

- What types of funding – public, private, user-based, etc. are used?
- Are the funding sources and splits different for the development stage and the maintenance / operation stage?

University of Edinburgh

- The simple answer is that the costs are paid by the university. The repository has been active since 2008.
- The first project funding in 2007 came from the DISK-UK Data Project – a collaboration with Southampton and Oxford Universities – this was a three year project which investigated how to get data librarians and institutional data managers to collaborate. All 3 institutions went on from this to host data or to have an independent data repository.

- The bigger element is the University of Edinburgh data service. This also provides active data storage, advice on data management plans, lots of other services. Also provided is a data safe haven and a closed data vault developed with university funding on the basis that they will have cost recovery on operations.
- Datashare is free for use, partly to encourage / incentivise data sharing. It is free but it has some limits. Each data set is limited to 100GB per item – not really suitable for Big Data. Files up to 20GB can be uploaded, for files that add up to more than 20GB, the depositors can speak to the curators to facilitate this.
- So there is a mixed funding model. Some covered by the university, some cost recovery from grants.
- As regards the overall budget in terms of costs and time / effort:
- Datashare is just one component of the function. The University of Edinburgh is well invested in the whole functional area.
- There are 7 people on the Research Data Support Team (some of whom are part time) and also systems people and data researchers.
- For the repository a portion of Data Librarian and Head, Research Data Support could be assigned, with 3 data research assistants, who approve, talk to researchers, check quality, and a part-time software developer.
- Ignoring others, such as people who run the data centre, probably 10% of the first person plus 30% of 3 people.
- So a bit over one FTE on support and around one half FTE on development.
- Other repositories are often also run on this sort of a shoestring.
- In December they were upgrading to a newer version of DSpace which will take about 2 months.
- So Edinburgh University has a really strong focus on Data services, and the repository is part of that.
- The library and IT are merged into information services here which is really useful for these sort of services.
- There may be a move to some being paid by research grant overheads, but that's not the case at the moment - Data share is free but Datavault, for restricted access, will have charges for more than 100 GB.
- Datavault is a long-term retention model where there is payment in advance for long term storage - whatever their funder requires.
- It is not accessible to the public but there will be a public metadata record - so still findable - though requests may be turned down.
- The clinical trials unit can choose Datashare or Datavault - they tend to prefer Datashare.
- A way has been found to use the embargo feature (there is a rolling embargo going). The aim is to be as open as possible.

Vivli

- For the launch of the platform grants were received from several philanthropic organisations; some of them represent end-users or fund clinical trials (as Gates Foundation).
- The funding sources and splits were not really different for the development stage and the maintenance / operation stage - the initial amount was a global envelope.

BioLINCC

- Publicly funded - by contract.

Question 3: Legal advice

- How is this handled? In-house staff or outsourced?
- What were the major requirements for legal advice?

University of Edinburgh

- The university legal office provides the legal services. They were consulted about Depositor Agreement.
- Because the depositors are all in the same legal entity (University of Edinburgh), they can say what to do but reluctant to deal with entities outside the university.
- There are ongoing attempts to make the depositors aware that we're taking over the rights now to manage the data.
 - It's more generic advice - not particularly involved in the day to day.
- If something came up about an item a take down policy would be invoked and the legal department consulted. So far no breaches.
- The risk of such breaches is not so high but the potential impact could be very serious.
- For the clinical trial data, barring explicit permission (e.g. video interviews), the data is anonymised. The depositors vouch that it is anonymised. But there is also the extra precaution of vetting access.
 - All data sets in the whole repository require the researchers to anonymise the data.
 - There is an anonymisation expert for data in the clinical trials unit.
 - That is not offered as a service at this point.

Vivli

- A legal firm is providing services as in kind contribution to the platform.
- The major requirements for legal advice were enquiries, legal agreements, GDPR; contracting is a significant part of the activities.

BioLINCC

- Obtained when needed through the NIH.
- As all studies were funded through NHBLI, there are 2 - 3 standard draft use agreements for users and no more flexibility in that regard.

Question 4: Metrics for Data Access Committee

- How many people are involved? Who are they? What are their costs and conditions?
- How are they selected? How often do they meet?
- How much review is required? (per request?)

University of Edinburgh

- Not used as such.

Vivli

- Wellcome Trust offers to do the review each time there is a request.

BioLINCC

- No formal DAC but individual identified who reviews requests for proposed use of data. Ensure that IRB waiver or review is satisfied, that data is fit for purpose, informed consent and that required information is provided.
- In general a few hours required per request.

Question 5: General Sustainability Considerations

For how long is funding secured / reliably anticipated?

Are there alternative plans in place to ensure sustainability?

University of Edinburgh

- When the Research Data Service was set up in 2011/12 and consolidated / made more formal in 2016/17, 350,000 pounds per year were committed to the university for data services as a whole. Datashare is an integral part of this service - a very early part.
- There is also the possibility to bid for development money for the service as a whole.
- They also have an academic led governance committee for the service as a whole - quarterly meetings. The chair of the group is the business service owner. Job is to make sure that they are fit for purpose.
- The Director of Information Services (CIO) and university have strong commitment to this.
- So there is effectively flat funding.
- As based in the library, it is quite a sustainable place, having been there for centuries.
- If dataspace shut down, there could be procedures to move, perhaps to Zenodo if necessary.
- There are change management procedures in place. There is also a huge training and awareness program - that the service exists, what the benefits of the repository are.
- Although required by funders, people have their ways of getting around these requirements.
- There are over 2,500 data sets in the repository - word of mouth spreads uptake.
- It was ensured that someone was depositing from each of the 21 schools to spread the word.
- Researchers are encouraged to use domain repositories, although this is not compulsory. Early on datashare was being called depository of last resort - this descriptor is not seen as ideal.
- Data may be better findable in a domain repository but there are lots of potential cracks in this system - sustainability, awareness, existence, convenience.

Vivli

- Any plans are confidential so not disclosed here.

BioLINCC

- NIH has a huge commitment to data sharing. The funding contracts, first awarded for 5 years in 2008, renewed.
- Now in first option year of 8 year current contract.
- Detailed plans beyond ongoing support confidential.

Question 6: Services provided (in addition to basic repository function)

- Are any separate services provided to data providers or data users?
 - (e.g. de-identification services, protected analysis environment)
- Can costs be approximately split between the costs for basic infrastructure and those for basic services?

University of Edinburgh

- Not as part of the repository but yes as part of the Research Data service.
- RDS divides services into Before, During and After. People are informed about costs.
- They have high performance computing which is out of the service but is offered. These costs should be included in a grant.
- The repository does not allow online analysis at all - have to download.
- They have a Services Page online which gives details.

Vivli

- Privacy Analytics (3rd party) offers de-identification services.
- Information about costs is confidential so not disclosed here.

BioLINCC

- The data uploaders themselves have to perform de-identification / anonymisation - BioLINCC only very rarely handles it.
- A full review to make sure that the documentation matches to the data is a significant cost in time and resources - varies hugely.
- Could be around 80 hours for a single study.

Question 7: Costs

- What were the major costs in developing the repository?
- What is the approximate split of costs between:
 - o software costs, technical costs, legal & admin costs?
- What functions, if any, are or were outsourced?
- Are there any other significant constituent cost areas?

University of Edinburgh

- The development costs are covered under Question 2.
- DSpace use is free. Payment is made for silver membership for Duraspace.
- Dspace is considered sustainable as so many places using and contributing to it.
- It is quite simple – this has advantages with high turnover of software developers.
- The hardware is free to us as an internal customer. Due to this high level commitment, terabytes of data and infrastructure.
- We are only about 3 terabytes so the costs for this not that significant - especially as done at scale.
- Everything is in-house, there is no outsourcing. We may consider buying in some DSpace expertise.
- There is no insurance.
- There is business continuity planning. There may be insurance built into the contract with the cloud provider.
- They don't like to have personal and sensitive data without specific consent in the repository. It is a risk reason
- Dspace is an internet tool and could in theory be hacked.
- A more secure system could be developed either on the internet or offline. DSpace is not the best choice for using data that is not secure.

Vivli

- The major cost was building the platform itself. The estimates given are treated as confidential so not disclosed here.

BioLINCC

- Costs were described in detail and inform the analysis in the paper, but the details are confidential and not disclosed here.